

Dark Energy is Gravitational Potential Energy or Energy of the Gravitational Field ¹

Hyoyoung Choi * ²

*Independent Researcher, Seoul, Republic of Korea

Abstract

When a bound object exerts gravity, the gravitational action of gravitational potential energy (gravitational binding energy) is also included. Therefore, even in the case of the universe, the gravitational action of gravitational potential energy must be considered. Gravitational potential energy generates a repulsive force because it has a negative equivalent mass. Mass energy (Mc^2) is an attractive component, and the equivalent mass ($-M_{gp}$) of gravitational potential energy is a repulsive component. Therefore, if $|(-M_{gp})c^2| < Mc^2$, there is a decelerated expansion, and if $|(-M_{gp})c^2| > Mc^2$, accelerated expansion is performed. $|(-M_{gp})c^2| = Mc^2$ is the inflection point from the decelerated expansion to the accelerated expansion. Dark energy is gravitational potential energy or the energy of the gravitational field. Dark energy arises because any positive energy (mass) contained within the range of gravitational interaction creates negative gravitational potential energy. While positive mass energy is proportional to M , absolute value of gravitational potential energy increases faster because gravitational potential energy is proportional to $-\frac{M^2}{R}$. Therefore, as the universe ages and the range of gravitational interaction expands, a situation arises where the negative gravitational potential energy becomes greater than the positive mass energy, and thus the universe is accelerating expansion. I present Friedmann equations and dark energy function obtained through gravitational potential energy or gravitational self-energy model. There is no cosmological constant and dark energy is a function of time. This model predicts an inflection point where dark energy becomes larger and more important than the energy of matter and radiation.

1. Gravitational action of the gravitational potential energy or gravitational field

The basis of modern cosmology is Einstein's 1915 field equation. However, this field equation has a singularity problem inside the black hole. In other words, the field equation created by Einstein is likely to be incomplete.

The fundamental principle of general relativity states that "all energy is a source of gravity". However, the field equation created by Einstein did not fully realize this principle.

In writing the field equation (48) we have assumed that the quantity $T^{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor of matter. In order to obtain a linear field equation we have left out the effect of the gravitational field upon itself. Because of this omission, our linear field equation has several (related) defects: (1) According to (48) matter acts on the gravitational field (changes the fields), but there is no mutual action of gravitational fields on matter; that is, the gravitational field can acquire energy-momentum from matter, but nevertheless the energy-momentum of matter is conserved ($\partial_\nu T^{\mu\nu} = 0$). This is an inconsistency. (2) Gravitational energy does not act as source of gravitation, in contradiction to the principle of equivalence. Thus, although Eq. (48) may be a fair approximation in the case of weak gravitational fields, it cannot be an exact equation.

¹This paper excerpted only the dark energy-related items from the following paper and added some research content. On the solution of the strong gravitational field, the solution of the Singularity problem, the origin of Dark energy and Dark matter [<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359329109>] or [<https://vixra.org/abs/2203.0096>]

²E-mail: 7icarus7@gmail.com

The obvious way to correct for our sin of omission is to include the energy-momentum tensor of the gravitational field in $T^{\mu\nu}$. This means that we take for the quantity $T^{\mu\nu}$ the total energy-momentum tensor of matter plus gravitation:

$$T^{\mu\nu} = T_{(m)}^{\mu\nu} + t^{\mu\nu} \quad [1]$$

The energy of the gravitational field must also function as a gravitational source. However, because it was difficult to define the energy-momentum of the gravitational field, Einstein could not complete the field equation including the gravitational action of the gravitational field [2]. Methods such as the Landau-Lifshitz pseudotensor [3] exist for describing the energy-momentum of a gravitational field, but not everyone agrees. Also, it seems that these pseudotensors are not developed enough to be applied to cosmology. By the way, it may be sufficient to include the equivalent mass density of gravitational self-energy in $T_{(m)}^{\mu\nu}$ without introducing $t^{\mu\nu}$.

The $T_{\mu\nu}$ in Einstein's original field equations is the equivalent mass of all forms of energy of the object, including binding energy, kinetic energy, and potential energy, as well as the mass in the free state. Thus, **when considering the energy density or mass density in cosmology, the gravitational potential energy density should also be reflected.**

Furthermore, according to Shell Theorem and Birkhoff's Theorem, in a spherically symmetric system, the gravitational effect at a given radius is determined only by the mass or energy content surrounded within that radius, and contributions from outside the shell do not affect the internal dynamics. Although the energy of the gravitational field is generally considered to be a global quantity and is difficult to localize in general relativity, the application of these theorems allows us to treat the gravitational field energy as a localized contribution within the shell (That is, the energy of the gravitational field is considered only in the $0 \leq r \leq R$ part). This approach is justified by including only the energy density, pressure, and other physical quantities inside the shell in deriving cosmological equations such as the Friedmann equation.

1.1. Negative mass (energy) density in standard cosmology

1.1.1. The logical structure behind the success of standard cosmology

From the second Friedmann equation or acceleration equation, ($c \equiv 1$) [4]

$$\frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} \right) = - \left(\frac{4\pi G}{3} \right) (\rho + 3P) \quad (1)$$

For the universe to expand acceleratingly, the right-hand side must be positive, and therefore $(\rho + 3P)$ must be negative. That is, for the universe to expand acceleratingly, a negative mass density is required. In the standard cosmology, it is explained by introducing an entity that has a positive mass (energy) density but exerts a negative pressure [4] [5] [6].

$$\rho_\Lambda + 3P = \rho_\Lambda + 3(-\rho_\Lambda) = -2\rho_\Lambda \quad (2)$$

However, if we expand the dark energy term, the final result is a negative mass density of $-2\rho_\Lambda$.

Let's look at the expression expressing $(\rho + 3P)$ as the critical density of the universe.

Matter + Dark Matter (app. 31.7%) : $\rho_m \approx \frac{1}{3}\rho_c$

Dark energy density (app. 68.3%) : $\rho_\Lambda \approx \frac{2}{3}\rho_c$

(Matter + Dark Matter)'s pressure : $3P_m \approx 0$

Dark energy's pressure : $3P_\Lambda = 3(-\rho_\Lambda) = -2\rho_c$

$$\rho + 3P \simeq \rho_m + \rho_\Lambda + 3(P_m + P_\Lambda) \simeq \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)\rho_c + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)\rho_c + 3\left(-\frac{2}{3}\right)\rho_c = (+1)\rho_c + (-2)\rho_c = (-1)\rho_c \quad (3)$$

$$\rho + 3P \simeq (+1)\rho_c + (-2)\rho_c = (-1)\rho_c \quad (4)$$

Standard cosmology is a form of positive mass density of $+1\rho_c$ and negative mass density of $-2\rho_c$. So, finally, the universe has a negative mass density of " $-\rho_c$ ", so accelerated expansion is taking

place. Because mass and energy are equivalent, the current universe is similar to a state in which negative energy is twice as much as positive energy. And the observable universe is in a state of negative energy.

1.1.2. The claim that vacuum energy and the cosmological constant have a negative pressure is wrong

In standard cosmology, accelerated expansion is impossible without a negative mass density. Negative mass density is an inevitable result of dimensional analysis. However, researchers who were reluctant to the negative mass could not accept the negative mass density, so they think of a mechanism that exerts negative pressure while having a positive energy density. However, the claim that vacuum energy and the cosmological constant have a negative pressure is wrong.

1.1.2.1. Sign of the negative pressure [7]

From the ideal gas equation of state,

$$PV = \frac{nMv_{rms}^2}{3} \quad (5)$$

In the kinetic theory of gas molecules, we know that pressure is directly related to kinetic energy.

we arrive at the acceleration equation.

$$\frac{d^2R}{dt^2} = -\left(\frac{4\pi G}{3}\right)(\rho + 3P)R$$

*Note that the effect of the pressure P is to slow down the expansion (assuming $P > 0$). If this seems counterintuitive, recall that **because the pressure is the same everywhere in the universe, both inside and outside the shell, there is no pressure gradient to exert a net force on the expanding sphere.** The answer lies in the motion of the particles that creates the fluid's pressure. **The equivalent mass of the particle's kinetic energy creates a gravitational attraction that slows down the expansion just as their actual mass does.** [4]*

In the acceleration equation, the pressure P is related to the momentum or kinetic energy of the particle. Therefore, it seems that in order for the pressure P to have a negative value, it must have negative momentum or negative kinetic energy. So, assuming that the pressure P term has a negative energy density is same assuming that it has negative kinetic energy. In order to have negative kinetic energy, it must have negative inertial mass or imaginary velocity. But, because they assumed a positive inertial mass (positive energy density), it is a logical contradiction.

$$K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 < 0 \quad (6)$$

$m < 0$ or $v = Vi$: negative mass or imaginary speed.

Negative mass contradicts the assumption of positive energy density, and energy density with imaginary speed is far from physical reality.

1.1.2.2. Size of the negative pressure [7]

In the case of matter, $P = 0$

In the case of radiation, $P = \frac{1}{3}\rho$

In the case of dark energy, $P = -\rho = -3(\frac{1}{3}\rho)$

Only considering the size (absolute value)

Since pressure is related to kinetic energy, in order to have a greater pressure than light, it seems that the subject must have a speed greater than light.

$$v = \sqrt{3}c \quad (7)$$

Considering even the negative sign

$$v = (\sqrt{3}c)i \quad (8)$$

We need energy density with imaginary super-luminous speed.

If we seriously consider the physical presence of $P = -\rho = -3(\frac{1}{3}\rho)$, we will find that there is a serious problem.

1.1.2.3. Incorrect application of $dU = -PdV$

In the equation $dU = -PdV$, researchers claim that negative pressure exists if the energy density remains constant as the volume increases. Is this claim correct?

1.1.2.3.1. This explanation is an inverted explanation

Since pressure is a property of an object, pressure exists first, and because of this pressure, changes in internal energy according to volume change appear.

That is, since pressure is positive, if $dV > 0$, then $dU < 0$.

Since the pressure is positive, if $dV < 0$, then $dU > 0$.

By the way, we use the logic “if $dV > 0$ and $dU > 0$, then $P < 0$ ”. How are you sure that this logic is correct?

1.1.2.3.2. $\rho + 3P = \rho + 3(-\rho) = -2\rho$

Mass density ρ and pressure P ($\frac{P}{c^2}$, $c \equiv 1$) are properties of the object to be analyzed. Both mass density ρ and pressure P are sources of gravity. It means that even if the region maintains a constant size without expanding or contracting, gravitational force is applied as much as $\rho + 3P = -2\rho$.

In other words, it suggests that the object (or energy density) has a gravity with a negative mass density of -2ρ . This is different from a vacuum with a positive energy density $+\rho$, which we think of.

1.1.2.3.3. $dU = -PdV$ is the expression obtained when the law of conservation of energy is established

However, in the case of vacuum energy and the cosmological constant, energy conservation does not hold. As the universe expands, the total energy in the system increases. Therefore, we cannot guarantee that $dU = -PdV$ holds. $dU = -PdV$ is an equation that holds when the energy of the system is conserved. However, researchers are applying this equation to vacuum energy or cosmological constant where the energy of the system is not conserved. This is problematic.

I am not sure if $dU = -PdV$ holds even for negative pressure. In the case of negative pressure, there may be a sign reversal. However, although this equation holds even in the case of negative pressure, its interpretation is as follows.

This equation holds true when substances in radius r_1 expand from r_1 to r_2 ($r_2 > r_1$), and have the same uniform density in r_1 and r_2 . In other words, it is argued that a negative pressure is required to create a uniform density effect **only with the material present in radius r_1** . But, vacuum energy is a form in which energy is newly generated by an increased volume. It is also energy that can be assumed to have an initial speed of $0 \sim c$. Considering the positive energy density, pressure term seems reasonable to assume $0 \sim \frac{1}{3}\rho$.

Even if vacuum energy with positive energy density is present, it is not certain whether it creates a negative pressure.

There is no physical entity that satisfies $\rho + 3P = \rho + 3(-\rho) = -2\rho$. Nothing has a kinetic energy component three times greater than that of light. Vacuum energy and cosmological constant has no negative pressure. **The negative pressure is due to incorrect application of $dU = -PdV$.**

Vacuum energy with positive energy density $+\rho$ does not have a negative pressure, but has a $0 \sim$ positive pressure. Because the pressure is related to the kinetic energy.

Researchers, who could not accept negative mass density, try to somehow create an accelerated expansion through the equation $\rho + 3P$, so assuming magic with positive energy density but negative pressure. As a result, we have created something imaginary, not a physical reality. It is not necessary for an entity to exist that exerts a negative pressure while having a positive energy density. It is sufficient that a positive energy component and a negative energy component exist. And negative energy components can be played by gravitational potential energy or energy in the gravitational field.

The vacuum energy model is a model with a positive mass density $+\rho$ and a negative pressure $3P = -3\rho$. On the other hand, the gravitational potential energy model is a model with a positive mass density $+\rho$ and

an equivalent mass density $-\rho_{gp}$ of gravitational potential energy. The equivalent mass density of gravitational potential energy will replace the role of negative pressure in standard cosmology.

1.2. The energy of a gravitational field is negative

Alan Guth said: [8]

The energy of a gravitational field is negative!

The positive energy of the false vacuum was compensated by the negative energy of gravity.

Stephen Hawking also argued that [9]

The matter in the universe is made out of positive energy. However, the matter is all attracting itself by gravity. Two pieces of matter that are close to each other have less energy than the same two pieces a long way apart, because you have to expend energy to separate them against the gravitational force that is pulling them together. Thus, in a sense, the gravitational field has negative energy. In the case of a universe that is approximately uniform in space, one can show that this negative gravitational energy exactly cancels the positive energy represented by the matter. So the total energy of the universe is zero.

Now twice zero is also zero. Thus the universe can double the amount of positive matter energy and also double the negative gravitational energy without violation of the conservation of energy.

Both argued that gravitational potential energy is negative energy and is the true energy that can cancel positive mass energy.

1.3. Gravitational self-energy or gravitational binding energy

The concept of gravitational self-energy (U_{gs}) is the total of gravitational potential energy (U_{gp}) possessed by a certain object M itself. Since a certain object M itself is a binding state of infinitesimal mass dMs , it involves the existence of gravitational potential energy among these dMs and is the value of adding up these. $M = \sum dM$.

Gravitational self-energy³ or Gravitational binding energy ($-U_{gs}$) in case of spherical uniform distribution is given by

$$U_{gs} = U_{gp} = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{R} \quad (9)$$

Treating the Earth as a continuous, classical mass distribution (with no gravitational self-energy in the elementary, subatomic particles), we find that its gravitational self-energy is about 4.6×10^{-10} times its rest-mass energy. The gravitational self-energy of the Moon is smaller, only about 0.2×10^{-10} times its rest-mass energy. - Gravitation and Spacetime [1]

All energy is a gravitational source, so gravitational potential energy is also a gravitational source.

The gravitational self-energy (or gravitational potential energy) is proportional to $-\frac{M^2}{R}$. Therefore, as the mass increases, the gravitational self-energy value increases.

In the case of Moon, $U_{gs-Moon} = (-1.89 \times 10^{-11})M_{Moon}c^2$

In the case of Earth, $U_{gs-Earth} = (-4.17 \times 10^{-10})M_{Earth}c^2$

In the case of the Sun, $U_{gs-Sun} = (-1.27 \times 10^{-4})M_{Sun}c^2$

In case of a Black hole, $U_{gs-Black-hole} = (-3.0 \times 10^{-1})M_{Black-hole}c^2$

$$U_{gs-Black-hole} = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{R} \approx -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{\left(\frac{2GM}{c^2}\right)} = -\frac{3}{10} Mc^2 \quad (10)$$

³Gravitational potential energy = Gravitational self-energy = - Gravitational binding energy \sim Energy of gravitational field. In Newtonian mechanics, all four energies are of the form $U = -k \frac{GM^2}{R}$, and the three energies are $k = \frac{3}{5}$ in the case of a spherical uniform distribution. Depending on the integration section, the energy of the gravitational field may be $k=3/5$ or may vary.

It can be seen that as the mass increases, the ratio of gravitational self-energy increases. It can be seen that the gravitational potential energy is about 1/10000 of the (free state) mass energy in the case of the sun and 30% of the (free state) mass energy of the black hole at the event horizon of the black hole.

So, now we can ask the following question. What about the universe with much greater mass?

1.4. Binding energy in the mass defect problem

Figure 1: In order for a system to form a bond state, a mass defect equal to the binding energy must occur.

Consider situations a) and c).

In a), the total mass of the two particle system is $2m$, and the total energy is $E_{T_1} = 2mc^2$

In c), is the total energy of the two particle system $E_{T_1} = 2mc^2$?

In c), when the two particle system act gravitationally on an external particle, will they act gravitationally with a gravitational mass of $2m$?

Are a), b) and c) the same mass or same state?

If you do not apply negative binding energy, the conclusions you get will not match the actual results.

In c), the total energy of the two particle system is

$$E_{T_1} = 2mc^2 - \frac{Gmm}{r} \quad (11)$$

In the dimensional analysis of energy, E has ML^2T^{-2} , so all energy can be expressed in the form of $(mass)X(velocity)^2$. So, $E = Mc^2$ holds for all kinds of energy. Here, M is the equivalent mass or relativistic mass. If we introduce the negative equivalent mass $-m_{gp}$ for the negative gravitational potential energy,

$$-\frac{Gmm}{r} = -m_{gp}c^2 \quad (12)$$

$$E_{T_1} = 2mc^2 - \frac{Gmm}{r} = 2mc^2 - m_{gp}c^2 = (2m - m_{gp})c^2 = m^*c^2 \quad (13)$$

The gravity of a composite particle composed of two objects acting on a mass m_3 that is relatively far away is

$$F = -\frac{Gm^*m_3}{R^2} = -\frac{G(2m - m_{gp})m_3}{R^2} = -\frac{G(2m)m_3}{R^2} - \frac{G(-m_{gp})m_3}{R^2} \quad (14)$$

That is, when considering the gravitational action of a bind system, not only the mass in its free state but also the binding energy term $(-m_{gp})$ should be considered. Alternatively, the gravitational

force acting on the bind system can be decomposed into a free-state mass term and an equivalent mass term of binding energy.

While we usually use the mass m^* of the bind system, we forget that m^* is “ $m - m_{binding-energy}$ ”. Gravitational potential energy is also a kind of binding energy. Therefore, the gravitational potential energy, which is the binding energy, must also be considered in the universe.

When a macroscopic object is subjected to gravitational force, the equation includes the gravitational term of the negative gravitational potential energy. In a normal case, since the term of gravitational potential energy is negligible compared to mass energy, it can be neglected. Alternatively, you can think of the mass of the gravitational source as the equivalent mass m^* including the gravitational potential energy, not the free mass. However, since the gravitational potential energy has a fairly large value near the Schwarzschild radius, it must be considered. The same is true of the universe.

Look at the second term again, it is the repulsive force (anti-gravity) term.

$$F_{gp} = + \frac{G(m_{gp})m_3}{R^2} \tag{15}$$

What if, in the observable universe, the second term is greater than the first term?

It can be seen that it has the potential to explain the accelerated expansion of the universe.

2. Dark energy is gravitational potential energy or the energy of the gravitational field

The universe is almost flat, and its mass density is also very low [4] [10]. Thus, Newtonian mechanics approximation can be applied. And, the following reasoning should not be denied by the assertion that “it is difficult to define the total energy in general relativity.”

Whether or not it is an appropriate approximation is not determined by current field equation and current general relativity. This is because the current field equation is an incomplete field equation that does not include the gravitational action of the gravitational field. When it is difficult to find a complete solution, we have found numerous solutions through approximation. The success of this approximation or inference must be determined by the model’s predictions and observations of the universe.

Equation (29.51, acceleration equation) is an illustration of Birkhoff’s theorem. In 1923 the American mathematician G.D.Birkhoff (1884-1944) proved quite generally that for a spherically symmetric distribution of matter, Einstein’s field equations have a unique solution. As a corollary, the acceleration of an expanding shell in our fluid universe is determined solely by the fluid lying within the shell. Equation (29.51) shows that the acceleration does not depend on any factors other than ρ , P , and R . Because Birkhoff’s theorem holds even when general relativity is included, it is quite important in the study of cosmology. [4]

By Birkhoff’s theorem, only the mass or energy component within the gravitational interaction range is important. If we find the positive energy $(Mc^2)^4$ and gravitational potential energy $((-M_{gp})c^2)$ values at each radius R of gravitational interaction, **positive energy is an attractive component, and the gravitational potential energy is a repulsive component.**

$$|(-M_{gp})c^2| < Mc^2 : \text{Decelerating expansion period}$$

$$|(-M_{gp})c^2| = Mc^2 : \text{Inflection point}$$

⁴Strictly speaking, the mass M should include the mass of all the masses that make up the observable universe when they were in a free state. However, since some objects are already bound, it is difficult to know the total mass in a free state. However, in general, gravitational self-energy can be ignored except for black holes. Also, since the mass of black holes is a small proportion of the total matter, the mass in a free state and the measured or estimated mass are very close.

$|(-M_{gp})c^2| > Mc^2$: Accelerating expansion period

Critical density value $\rho_c = 8.50 \times 10^{-27} [kgm^{-3}]$ [10] was used. In practice the density changes, but we just need to look at the trend.

2.1. Comparison of magnitudes of mass energy and gravitational potential energy in the cosmic event horizon $R = 16.7Gly$

2.1.1. At $R = 16.7Gly$, total mass energy

Cosmic event horizon $16.7Gly$. Since the universe is almost flat spacetime, the total mass energy (include radiation energy) in the $R = 16.7Gly$ is

$$Mc^2 = \frac{4\pi R^3 \rho c^2}{3} = 1.28 \times 10^{70} [kgm^2 s^{-2}] \quad (16)$$

2.1.2. At $R = 16.7Gly$, gravitational potential energy

$$U = -\frac{3 GM^2}{5 R} = -\frac{16\pi^2 GR^5 \rho^2}{15} = -4.99 \times 10^{69} [kgm^2 s^{-2}] \quad (17)$$

2.1.3. Comparison of magnitudes of total mass energy and gravitational potential energy in the $R = 16.7Gly$

$$\frac{U}{Mc^2} = \frac{-4.99 \times 10^{69}}{1.28 \times 10^{70}} = -0.39 \quad (18)$$

In the calculation, the current critical density value was used, but when the range of gravitational interaction is $16.7Gly$, the density is different from now. So, just look at the logic.

In the $R = 16.7Gly$, the repulsive component is smaller than the attractive component. In this period, the universe is decelerating expansion. That is, when the range of gravitational interaction is $16.7Gly$, the dark energy component is smaller than that of matter. This period is a period of decelerated expansion.

2.2. The inflection point that changes from decelerated expansion to accelerated expansion

The inflection point R_{gp} is that the range of gravitational interaction at the transition from material dominance to dark energy dominance. The range of gravitational interaction at the transition from a period of predominant attraction to a period of predominant repulsion.

If the mass energy and the gravitational potential energy are equal, then

$$Mc^2 = \left| -\frac{3 GM^2}{5 R_{gp}} \right| \quad (19)$$

$$R_{gp} = \sqrt{\frac{5c^2}{4\pi G\rho}} \quad (20)$$

We only need to understand the general flow and possibility, so let's get R_{gp} by putting in the current critical density value. If we know the exact density function, we can find the exact inflection point.

$$R_{gp} = \sqrt{\frac{5c^2}{4\pi G\rho}} = 26.2Gly \quad (21)$$

Assuming that the average density is approximately 1.25 times the current average density, we get $R_{gp} = 23.7Gly$.

Assuming that the average density is approximately 1.5 times the current average density, we get $R_{gp} = 21.4Gly$.

Assuming that the average density is approximately 2 times the current average density, we get $R_{gp} = 18.7Gly$.

Comparing the data from the existing particle horizon graph, it is estimated that it is approximately 5 to 7 billion years ago from the present. This is similar to the result of standard cosmology [4]. This model includes the transition of the universe to the period of decelerated expansion, the inflection point, and the period of accelerated expansion.

Figure 2: Particle horizon vs time [11]. **About 5-7 billion years ago, it passed the inflection point 18.7 ~ 26.2Gly.** About 5 to 7 billion years ago, it can be said that the universe entered a period of accelerated expansion. The inflection point is affected by the density.

2.3. Comparison of magnitudes of mass energy and gravitational potential energy in the observable universe

2.3.1. At $R = 46.5Gly$, total mass energy

$$Mc^2 = \frac{4\pi R^3 \rho c^2}{3} = 2.71 \times 10^{71} [kgm^2s^{-2}] \quad (22)$$

2.3.2. At $R = 46.5Gly$, Gravitational potential energy

$$U = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{R} = -\frac{16\pi^2 GR^5 \rho^2}{15} = -8.35 \times 10^{71} [kgm^2s^{-2}] \quad (23)$$

2.3.3. In the observable universe, the ratio of total mass energy to gravitational potential energy

$$\frac{U}{Mc^2} = \frac{-8.35 \times 10^{71}}{2.751 \times 10^{71}} = -3.08 \quad (24)$$

The repulsive force component is approximately 3.08 times the attractive force component. So, the universe is accelerating expansion.

2.4. Result summary

At the range of gravitational interaction $R=16.7Gly$, $(-M_{gp})c^2 = (-0.39M)c^2$

$|(-M_{gp})c^2| < Mc^2$: Decelerating expansion period

At the range of gravitational interaction $R=26.2\text{Gly}$, $(-M_{gp})c^2 = (-1.00M)c^2$

$|(-M_{gp})c^2| = Mc^2$: Inflection point (About 5-7 billion years ago, consistent with standard cosmology.)

At the range of gravitational interaction $R=46.5\text{Gly}$, $(-M_{gp})c^2 = (-3.08M)c^2$

$|(-M_{gp})c^2| > Mc^2$: Accelerating expansion period

2.5. In the standard cosmology, the ratio of attractive and repulsive components

The following ratio is approximate ratio obtained from standard cosmology [10].

$$\frac{M_{repulsive}}{M_{attractive}} = \frac{-3\rho_{\Lambda}}{\rho_m + \rho_{\Lambda}} = \frac{-3(0.683\rho)}{0.317\rho + 0.683\rho} = -2.05 \quad (25)$$

At 16.7Gly , the attraction component is larger than the repulsive component, whereas at 46.5Gly , the repulsive component is 3.08 times larger than the attractive component. In the middle, there is an inflection point that changes from decelerated expansion to accelerated expansion. About 5-7 billion years ago, similar to the predictions of standard cosmology.

Although there is a slight difference between the two values, it is not an astronomical error, so it is likely to be resolved later. It is possible that kinetic energy, general relativity, density function, cosmological effects, assumption of uniformly distribution, or differences in cosmological models may explain the difference between the two values.

2.6. Regarding the cause of the error

2.6.1. New formula for calculating gravitational self-energy

According to the principle of general relativity, gravitational potential energy is also a source of gravity. Therefore, there is a problem in the conventional expression of gravitational self-energy.

Looking at the formula we use to find gravitational self-energy,

$$M' = \frac{4\pi}{3}r^3\rho \quad (26)$$

$$dm = \rho r^2 dr \sin\theta d\theta d\varphi \quad (27)$$

$$dU_{gs} = -G\frac{M'm}{r} \quad (28)$$

In the existing gravitational self-energy equation, the gravitational action due to negative gravitational self-energy is omitted from the internal mass M' term. The equivalent mass of gravitational self-energy must also be reflected in the M' term.

$$M^* = M' - M_{gs}' = M' - \frac{3GM'^2}{5rc^2} = \frac{4\pi}{3}r^3\rho - \frac{16\pi^2G}{15c^2}r^5\rho^2 \quad (29)$$

$$dU_{gs} = -G\frac{M^*dm}{r} = -G\frac{(M' - M_{gs}')(\rho r^2 dr \sin\theta d\theta d\varphi)}{r} = -\left(\frac{4\pi G\rho^2}{3}r^4 - \frac{16\pi^2G^2\rho^3}{15c^2}r^6\right)dr \sin\theta d\theta d\varphi \quad (30)$$

$$U_{gs} = -\frac{4\pi G\rho^2}{3}\int_0^R r^4 dr \int_0^\pi \sin\theta d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi + \frac{16\pi^2G^2\rho^3}{15c^2}\int_0^R r^6 dr \int_0^\pi \sin\theta d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \quad (31)$$

$$U_{gs} = -\frac{(4\pi\rho)^2G}{3}\int_0^R r^4 dr + \frac{(4\pi\rho)^3G^2}{15c^2}\int_0^R r^6 dr = -\frac{3GM^2}{5R} + \frac{(4\pi\rho)^3G^2}{15c^2}\frac{1}{7}R^7 \quad (32)$$

$$U_{gs} = -\frac{3GM^2}{5R}\left(1 - \frac{3GM}{7Rc^2}\right) \quad (33)$$

$$U_{gs-T} = U_{gs-M} + U_{gs-gs} = \left(-\frac{3GM^2}{5R}\right) + \left(\frac{3GM}{7Rc^2}\frac{3GM^2}{5R}\right) \quad (34)$$

The first term is the gravitational self-energy term produced by the positive mass M , and the second term is the gravitational self-energy term created by the equivalent mass of the gravitational self-energy of the internal mass M' . The second term is very small in the case of ordinary matter and can be neglected, but it cannot be neglected when there are sufficiently many substances such as the universe.

The above equation depends on the process or pathway that collects the matters. However, since the present cosmic situation does not collect the materials in the free state, the application of this formula does not seem reasonable. The present universe is a case in which, as the universe ages, the range of gravitational interaction expands, and objects that were outside the gravitational interaction suddenly participate in gravitational interaction, and gravitational potential energy is generated.

Comparing the first and second terms, At $R = 46.5Gly$,

$$U_{gs} = -\frac{3}{5}\frac{GM^2}{R}\left(1 - \frac{3}{7}\frac{GM}{Rc^2}\right) = (1.2)\left(\frac{3}{5}\frac{GM^2}{R}\right) \quad (35)$$

If we look for the case where $\left(1 - \frac{3}{7}\frac{GM}{Rc^2}\right) = 0$,

$$R = \frac{3}{7}\frac{GM}{c^2} = \frac{3}{14}R_S = \frac{5}{7}R_{gs} \quad (36)$$

2.6.2. Universe structure correction variable or Gravitational self-energy correction variable $\beta(t)$

Another possibility related to the cause of the error is the mass problem of strongly bound objects, such as stars, black holes and galaxies. The mass of a star or galaxy observed from the outside will already be the total mass reflecting the value of its own gravitational energy. On the other hand, the gravitational self-energy equation assumes a uniform distribution and calculates all gravitational potential energy terms. In other words, there is a possibility that the gravitational self-energy term is over-calculated.

By introducing the universe structure (correction) variable $\beta(t)$, if we correct the gravitational self-energy value,

$$\beta(t) = \frac{2.05}{3.08} = 0.665 \quad (37)$$

$$U_{gs}' = \beta(t)U_{gs} = (0.665)\left(-\frac{3}{5}\frac{GM^2}{R}\right) \quad (38)$$

Although the universe structure correction variable $\beta(t)$ is a variable in all time, it is thought that it can be treated almost like a constant since the change will be small after the galactic structure is formed. Therefore, β can be called a universe structure constant.

2.6.3. Because of the propagation velocity of the field, it is possible that some matter within the range of gravitational interaction is not participating in gravitational interaction

That is, it is possible that the gravitational force has not yet been transmitted from one end to the other. There is a possibility of overcalculation of gravitational potential energy.

2.6.4. Additionally, there may be general relativistic and cosmological effects

In addition to 2.6.1. - 2.6.4. mentioned here, there may be factors that need to be corrected. In summary, I will use the universe structure correction variable $\beta(t)$.

3. New Friedmann equations and cosmological constant function obtained by the gravitational potential energy model

The Friedmann equation can be obtained from the field equation. The basic form can also be obtained through Newtonian mechanics. If the object to be analyzed has spherical symmetry, from the second Newton's law, $R(t) = a(t)R$

$$m \frac{d^2 R(t)}{dt^2} = -\frac{GM(t)m}{R(t)^2} \quad (39)$$

$$m \frac{d^2 a(t)R}{dt^2} = -Gm \frac{\frac{4\pi}{3} a^3(t) R^3 \rho(t)}{a^2(t) R^2} = -Gm \frac{4\pi}{3} a(t) R \rho(t) \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}(t)}{a(t)} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \rho(t) \quad (41)$$

By adding pressure, we can create an acceleration equation.

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho + \frac{3P}{c^2} \right) \quad (42)$$

Let's look at the origin of mass density ρ here! What does ρ come from? It comes from the total mass M inside the shell. The universe is a combined state because it contains various matter, radiation, and energy. Therefore, the total mass m^* including the binding energy must be entered, not the mass “ $2m$ ” in the free state. “ $m^* = 2m + (-m_{gp})$ ”, i.e. gravitational potential energy must be considered.

The acceleration equation is derived from general relativity. However, I think that the fact that it can be derived from Newtonian mechanics also increases the likelihood of success in Newtonian mechanical reasoning.

Even when using the FLRW metric, there is a relative distance $a(t)R$ or radius defined by the scale factor $a(t)$, and there is a mass density. If we multiply the mass (energy) density by the coefficient, it will be restored to the mass in $a(t)R$. As long as internal masses are applied, the gravitational potential energy between their internal mass terms always seems applicable.

The current cosmological constant model is

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (43)$$

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G \rho}{3} - \frac{kc^2}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda c^2}{3} \quad (44)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho + \frac{3P}{c^2} \right) + \frac{\Lambda c^2}{3} \quad (45)$$

3.1. In the gravitational potential energy model, Friedmann equations

In the gravitational potential energy model, if we derive the Friedmann equation,

$$-M_{gp} = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{Rc^2} \beta(t) = -\frac{16\pi^2 GR^5(t) \rho^2(t)}{15c^2} \beta(t) \quad (46)$$

$$-\rho_{gp} = \frac{-M_{gp}}{V} = -\frac{4\pi GR^2 \rho^2}{5c^2} \beta(t) \quad (47)$$

$-\rho_{gp}$ is the equivalent mass density of gravitational potential energy, and $\beta(t)$ is the universe structure correction variable. Instead of mass density ρ , we have $(\rho) + (-\rho_{gp})$. $R(t)$ is the radius of gravitational interaction.

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left((\rho - \rho_{gp}) + \frac{3P}{c^2} \right) = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho + \frac{3P}{c^2} \right) + \frac{4\pi G}{3} \rho_{gp} \quad (48)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho(t) + \frac{3P}{c^2} \right) + \frac{\beta(t)}{15} \left(\frac{4\pi GR(t) \rho(t)}{c} \right)^2 \quad (49)$$

Dark energy term and Cosmological constant term

$$\frac{\Lambda c^2}{3} = \frac{\beta(t)}{15} \left(\frac{4\pi GR(t) \rho(t)}{c} \right)^2 \quad (50)$$

$$\Lambda(t) = \beta(t) \left(\frac{4\pi GR(t) \rho(t)}{\sqrt{5}c^2} \right)^2 = \beta \left(\frac{4\pi GR \rho}{\sqrt{5}c^2} \right)^2 \quad (51)$$

First Friedmann equation

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G\rho}{3} - \frac{kc^2}{a^2} + \frac{\beta(t)}{15} \left(\frac{4\pi GR\rho}{c}\right)^2 \quad (52)$$

Second Friedmann equation or acceleration equation

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho + \frac{3P}{c^2}\right) + \frac{\beta(t)}{15} \left(\frac{4\pi GR\rho}{c}\right)^2 \quad (53)$$

To see if the derived equation is probable, let's find the value of the cosmological constant.

$$\Lambda = \frac{\beta(t)}{5} \left(\frac{4(3.14)(6.67 \times 10^{-11} m^3 kg^{-1} s^{-2})(46.5 \times 9.46 \times 10^{24} m)(8.50 \times 10^{-27} kg m^{-3})}{(2.99 \times 10^8 m s^{-1})^2} \right)^2 \quad (54)$$

$$\Lambda = \frac{\beta(t)}{5} \left(\frac{4\pi GR\rho}{c^2}\right)^2 = (2.455 \times 10^{-52} m^{-2})\beta(t) \quad (55)$$

The value obtained from the Planck satellite [10] is,

$$\Lambda = 3\left(\frac{H_0}{c}\right)^2 \Omega_\Lambda = 1.1056 \times 10^{-52} m^{-2} \quad (56)$$

Now, we get the universe structure variable (or constant)

$$\beta(t_{now}) = \frac{1.1056 \times 10^{-52} m^{-2}}{2.455 \times 10^{-52} m^{-2}} = 0.450 \quad (57)$$

Even with rough estimates without any correction, we find that the cosmological constant term (dark energy) obtained from the gravitational potential energy model is very close to the observations

First Friedmann equation

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G\rho}{3} - \frac{kc^2}{a^2} + 3\left(\frac{2\pi GR\rho}{5c}\right)^2 \quad (58)$$

Second Friedmann equation, acceleration equation

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho + \frac{3P}{c^2}\right) + 3\left(\frac{2\pi GR\rho}{5c}\right)^2 \quad (59)$$

Dark energy term

$$\frac{\Lambda(t)c^2}{3} = \frac{\beta(t)}{15} \left(\frac{4\pi GR(t)\rho(t)}{c}\right)^2 = 3\left(\frac{2\pi GR\rho}{5c}\right)^2 \quad (60)$$

$$\Lambda(t) = \left(\frac{6\pi GR(t)\rho(t)}{5c^2}\right)^2 \quad (61)$$

$R(t)$ is the radius of gravitational interaction. In the gravitational potential energy model, if $\rho(t) \propto \frac{1}{R(t)}$, it is possible that the density of dark energy seems to be constant. However, I think that the density of dark energy will change.

Note that the gravitational potential energy model and the cosmological constant model have different elements. For example, the gravitational potential energy model has a negative energy density and does not assume negative pressure. In addition, the dark energy density is a constant in the cosmological constant model, but the dark energy density is a variable in the gravitational potential energy model. Since $R(t)$ and $\rho(t)$ are functions of time, **the dark energy (or cosmological constant term) is a function of time.**

3.2. In the gravitational field's energy model, Friedmann equations

To incorporate the energy of the gravitational field into the Friedmann equations, we consider only the portion of the gravitational field's energy contained within a spherical shell of radius R , leveraging the principles

of the Shell Theorem and Birkhoff's Theorem. According to these theorems, in a spherically symmetric system, the gravitational effects at a given radius are determined solely by the mass or energy content enclosed within that radius, while contributions from outside the shell do not affect the internal dynamics. Although the energy of the gravitational field is generally considered a global quantity and challenging to localize in general relativity, applying these theorems allows us to treat the enclosed fraction of the gravitational field's energy as a localized contribution within the shell. This approach justifies including only the energy density, pressure, and other physical quantities inside the shell when deriving cosmological equations such as the Friedmann equations.

Following this rationale, we calculate the energy density of the gravitational field within the shell as:

From the similarity of gravity and electromagnetic force, the energy density of the gravitational field is

$$E(r) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Qr}{R^3} \quad (62)$$

$$g(r) = \frac{GMr}{R^3} \quad (63)$$

$$\epsilon(r) = -\frac{g(r)^2}{8\pi G} = -\frac{GM^2r^2}{8\pi R^6} \quad (64)$$

The total energy of the gravitational field within radius R is then obtained by integrating over the volume:

$$U_{gf} = \int_0^R \epsilon(r) 4\pi r^2 dr = \int_0^R \left(-\frac{GM^2}{2R^6}\right) r^4 dr = -\frac{1}{10} \frac{GM^2}{R} = \frac{1}{6} U_{gp} \quad (65)$$

Larger values are possible in the case of the Landau-Lifshiz pseudotensor and the energy-momentum tensor of the gravitational field discovered by Grishchuk, Petrov and Popova [13].

For instance, in harmonic coordinates the Landau-Lifshiz symmetric pseudotensor and the energy-momentum tensor of the gravity field, which was found by Grishchuk, Petrov and Popova (1984), has a negative energy density of the weak static field :

$$t_{LL}^{00} = -\frac{7}{8\pi G} \left(\vec{\nabla}\phi_N\right)^2, \text{ and}$$

$$t_{GPP}^{00} = -\frac{11}{8\pi G} \left(\vec{\nabla}\phi_N\right)^2$$

The equivalent mass density of the gravitational field is

$$-\rho_{gf} = \frac{1}{6}(-\rho_{gp}) \quad (66)$$

In the classical model under spherical symmetry, the gravitational field's energy and the gravitational potential energy share a similar functional form ($U = -k\frac{GM^2}{R}$), differing only in their coefficients. Consequently, only the value of $\beta(t)$ differs, and the Friedmann equations retain the same form.

Based on current calculation results, the gravitational potential energy appears to be more suitable for modeling dark energy than the gravitational field energy. However, the approach of restricting the gravitational field's energy to the enclosed portion within the shell provides a consistent framework for incorporating such global effects into local cosmological dynamics.

$$\beta(t) = 2.70 \quad (67)$$

$$\Lambda(t) = \frac{1}{6} \frac{\beta(t)}{5} \left(\frac{4\pi GR(t)\rho(t)}{c^2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{6\pi GR(t)\rho(t)}{5c^2}\right)^2 \quad (68)$$

3.3. Force equation

$$F = -\frac{GM'm}{r^2} = -\frac{G(M_{fr} - M_{gp})m}{r^2} = -\frac{GM_{fr}m}{r^2} + \frac{G\left(\frac{4\pi r^3}{3}\rho_{gp}\right)m}{r^2} \quad (69)$$

We need to find the equivalent mass density ρ_{gp} of the gravitational potential energy that exists within the radius r . And this ρ_{gp} can be found from the total gravitational potential energy that exists within the range of gravitational interaction.

$$U_{gp} = -M_{gp}c^2 = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM_{fr}^2}{R_m} = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{G(\frac{4\pi R_m^3}{3}\rho)^2}{R_m} \quad (70)$$

R_m : Radius of distribution of matter and energy

M_{fr} : Total mass when the masses that make up the object are in a free state

$$\frac{4\pi R_m^3}{3}(-\rho_{gp})c^2 = -\frac{3}{5}(\frac{4\pi}{3})^2 GR_m^5 \rho^2 \quad (71)$$

$$-\rho_{gp} = -(\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM_{fr}}{c^2 R_m})\rho \quad (72)$$

$$F = -\frac{G(M_{fr} - M_{gp})m}{r^2} = -\frac{GM_{fr}m}{r^2} + \frac{G(\frac{4\pi r^3}{3}\rho_{gp}\beta)m}{r^2} = -\frac{GM_{fr}m}{r^2} + (\frac{4\pi G\rho_{gp}\beta}{3})mr \quad (73)$$

$$F = -\frac{GM_{fr}m}{r^2} + (\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM_{fr}}{c^2 R_m})\rho\beta)mr = -\frac{GM_{fr}m}{r^2} + (\frac{4\pi}{5} \frac{G^2}{c^2} \frac{M_{fr}}{R_m}\rho\beta)mr \quad (74)$$

$$\frac{F}{m} = \ddot{r} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}\rho r + \frac{\beta}{15}(\frac{4\pi GR_m\rho}{c})^2 r \quad (75)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{r}}{r} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}\rho + \frac{\beta}{15}(\frac{4\pi GR_m\rho}{c})^2 \quad (76)$$

If we put the pressure term, we see that this equation is identical to the acceleration equation obtained above. In the observable universe, $R = R_m$

$$\frac{\ddot{r}}{r} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\rho + \frac{3P}{c^2}) + \frac{\beta(t)}{15}(\frac{4\pi GR_m\rho}{c})^2 \quad (77)$$

4. Forms of expansion

4.1. When new material is introduced within the radius of gravitational interaction

According to the observation results so far, the dark energy density seems to be a constant. One way to explain these results is to hypothesize the introduction or creation of new substances. Since the cosmological constant model explains the phenomenon by assuming a uniform energy density, let's try to explain it through dynamics here.

The dark energy term suggested by gravitational potential energy model is as follows.

$$\frac{1}{3}\Lambda(t)c^2 = \frac{\beta(t)}{15}(\frac{4\pi Ga(t)R\rho(t)}{c})^2 = 3(\frac{2\pi GR(t)\rho(t)}{5c})^2 \quad (78)$$

Then, in order for this dark energy term to look like a constant, the following relationship needs to be established.

$$\rho(t) \propto \frac{1}{R(t)} \quad (79)$$

When a matter within a radius R expands to $2R$, its density drops to $1/2^3$. However, the above equation suggests that when R is changed to $2R$, the density drops only by $1/2$. Therefore, other kinetic property must exist.

Let's assume the following situation. Matter and galaxies are moving according to the Hubble-Lemaitre law. Assume that the gravitational field is moving at a higher speed than these. The propagation speed of the gravitational field will have "speed of space expansion" + "speed of light".

Then, over time, the amount of matter and galaxies that enter into gravitational interactions will increase. This increase in matter and galaxies has the effect of increasing gravitational potential energy. When R_0 is changed to $2R_0$, if the mass is increased by 8, the density remains the same. When R_0 is changed to $2R_0$, if the mass is 4 times, the density is halved.

Therefore, the point we need to find is R_x , which has a mass 4 times greater than its mass at R_0 .

$$M_x = \frac{4\pi R_x^3}{3} \rho_0 = 4 \left(\frac{4\pi R_0^3}{3} \rho_0 \right) \quad (80)$$

$$R_x = (4)^{\frac{1}{3}} R_0 \simeq 1.587 R_0 \quad (81)$$

When R_0 expands by k times, the value of R_x whose mass is k times: $R_x = (\frac{k^3}{2}) R_0$
Comparing the average speed of the field with the average speed of the matter in R_x ,

$$V_{R_0-Field} = \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta t} = \frac{2R_0 - R_0}{\Delta t} = \frac{R_0}{\Delta t} \quad (82)$$

$$V_{R_x-Matter} = \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta t} = \frac{2R_0 - R_x}{\Delta t} = (0.413) \frac{R_0}{\Delta t} = (0.413) V_{R_0-Field} \quad (83)$$

$$V_{R_0-Field} = 2.42 V_{R_x-Matter} \quad (84)$$

At a time when $a(t)R$ is about half of the current universe, if the speed of the field is about 2.4 times faster than the speed of matter, dark energy appears to be a constant. In addition, it can be explained through the addition of new energy such as vacuum energy, not the dynamic explanation.

4.2. When vacuum energy exists and the speed of expansion of matter and the speed of transfer of gravitational interaction are the same [13]

When vacuum energy exists, the total amount of matter within the range of gravitational interaction is conserved.

$$M_0 = \frac{4\pi}{3} \rho_{m,0} R_0^3 = \frac{4\pi}{3} \rho_{m,t} R_t^3 \quad (85)$$

$$\rho_{m,t} = \left(\frac{R_0}{R_t} \right)^3 \rho_{m,0} \quad (86)$$

$$E_{ME} = M(t)c^2 = \frac{4\pi c^2}{3} (\rho_{m,t} + \rho_{ve}) R_t^3 = \frac{4\pi c^2}{3} \left(\left(\frac{R_0}{R_t} \right)^3 \rho_{m,0} + \rho_{ve} \right) R_t^3 \quad (87)$$

$$U_{gp} = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM(t)^2}{R(t)} = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM \left(\frac{4\pi R_t^3 (\rho_{m,t} + \rho_{ve})}{3} \right)}{R_t} = -\frac{4\pi GM R_t^2 (\rho_{m,t} + \rho_{ve})}{5} \quad (88)$$

Strictly speaking, if density is a function of time, then the gravitational self-energy equation is presumed to be different from the uniform density equation. (The gravitational self-energy density depends on the process by which the mass gathers.) This is left for future research, and here I will consider only the beginning and end of the process. Since both the beginning and the end have uniform density, applying the uniform density equation,

$$\frac{U_{gp}}{E_{ME}} = \frac{-\frac{4\pi GM(t)R(t)^2(\rho_m(t)+\rho_{ve})}{5}}{M(t)c^2} = -\frac{4\pi G(R_t^2 \rho_{m,t} + R_t^2 \rho_{ve})}{5c^2} \quad (89)$$

$$\frac{U_{gp}}{E_{ME}} = -\left(\frac{3GM_0}{5c^2} \frac{1}{R_t} + \frac{4\pi G}{5c^2} R_t^2 \rho_{ve} \right) \quad (90)$$

As R increases, the first term goes to 0, but the second term increases in proportion to R^2 . In other words, the vacuum energy term becomes more important as time goes on.

A model like this can also be used to solve the current dark energy problem. Note that, in the Gravitational Potential Energy Model, vacuum energy does not have negative pressure. Although energy density always remains constant, positive energy density does not have negative pressure because pressure is related to kinetic

energy [4]. Since the gravitational potential energy is a negative energy component, there is no need to artificially assume a negative pressure.

4.3. Case where the radius of gravitational interaction increases over time, and mass M also changes

$$E_T(t) = M(t)c^2 - \frac{3}{5} \frac{GM(t)^2}{R(t)} \quad (91)$$

$$F = \frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{d(MV)}{dt} = V \frac{dM}{dt} + M \frac{d^2R}{dt^2} \quad (92)$$

$$F = -\frac{dE_T}{dR} = -\left[\frac{dM}{dR} c^2 - \frac{3G}{5} \left(\frac{2M}{R} \frac{dM}{dR} - \frac{M^2}{R^2} \right) \right] \quad (93)$$

$$M \frac{d^2R}{dt^2} + \frac{dR}{dt} \frac{dM}{dt} = -\left[\frac{dM}{dR} c^2 - \frac{3G}{5} \left(\frac{2M}{R} \frac{dM}{dR} - \frac{M^2}{R^2} \right) \right] \quad (94)$$

$$\frac{dM}{dR} = 4\pi R^2 \rho + \frac{4\pi}{3} R^3 \frac{d\rho}{dR} \quad (95)$$

$$M \frac{d^2R}{dt^2} = -\left[\frac{dM}{dR} c^2 - \frac{3G}{5} \left(\frac{2M}{R} \frac{dM}{dR} - \frac{M^2}{R^2} \right) \right] - \left(\frac{dR}{dt} \right)^2 \frac{dM}{dR} \quad (96)$$

$$\frac{d^2R}{dt^2} = \frac{1}{M} \left[\frac{6G}{5} \frac{M}{R} - c^2 - \left(\frac{dR}{dt} \right)^2 \right] \left(4\pi R^2 \rho + \frac{4\pi}{3} R^3 \frac{d\rho}{dR} \right) - \frac{3}{5} G \frac{M}{R^2} \quad (97)$$

$$\frac{d^2R}{dt^2} = \left[\frac{8\pi G}{5} R^2 \rho - c^2 - \left(\frac{dR}{dt} \right)^2 \right] \left(\frac{3}{R} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dR} \right) - \frac{4\pi G}{5} R \rho \quad (98)$$

1) The acceleration equation applying the initial cosmological conditions (If $R = ct$, $\rho = \rho_0$) is as follows:

$$\frac{d^2R}{dt^2} = 4\pi G \rho_0 R - \frac{6c^2}{R} \quad (99)$$

First term ($4\pi G \rho_0 R$): This term has a positive value and is proportional to R . This term represents the effect of accelerated expansion as the gravitational potential energy (negative value) increases. As R increases in the high density (ρ_0) state of the early universe, the effect of this term increases, leading to accelerated expansion. As the range of gravitational interactions increases, the negative gravitational potential energy exceeds the positive mass energy, which is consistent with the mechanism by which accelerated expansion occurs.

The second term ($-\frac{6c^2}{R}$): This term has a negative value and is inversely proportional to R . When R is very small (in the very early universe), the absolute value of this term is very large and acts as a strong force to suppress the expansion. This can be seen as a part of the system that is related to the positive mass energy.

Initiation of accelerated expansion: The point at which acceleration becomes zero, i.e., the critical radius at which expansion is converted to acceleration, R_{crit} is available as follows:

$$\frac{d^2R}{dt^2} = 4\pi G \rho_0 R - \frac{6c^2}{R} = 0 \quad (100)$$

$$R_{crit} = \sqrt{\frac{3c^2}{2\pi G \rho_0}} \quad (101)$$

If the radius R of the gravitational interaction is greater than this R_{crit} , then the $4\pi G \rho_0 R$ term becomes greater than the $-\frac{6c^2}{R}$ term, resulting in a positive acceleration and the onset of accelerated expansion.

2) If $R = kct$, $\rho = \frac{A}{R}$, (k and A are constants)

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} = \frac{12\pi GA}{5} - \frac{2c^2(1+k^2)}{R} \quad (102)$$

When R is small, deceleration may prevail, and when R is large, it may be accelerated or decelerated by a constant term (depending on the sign and magnitude of A).

3) If $R = kct$, $\rho = \frac{B}{R^2}$, (k and B are constants)

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} = \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{4\pi GB}{5} - c^2(1+k^2) \right) \quad (103)$$

In this case, the acceleration is inversely proportional to the radius R , and its sign is determined by the constant value within the parentheses. If we denote the value within the parentheses as $K = (\frac{4\pi GB}{5} - c^2(1+k^2))$, then the acceleration equation becomes $\frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} = \frac{K}{R}$.

If $K > 0$ (i.e., $\frac{4\pi GB}{5} > c^2(1+k^2)$), the acceleration is positive ($\ddot{R} > 0$), and the universe undergoes accelerated expansion. However, the magnitude of this acceleration decreases as R increases.

If $K < 0$ (i.e., $\frac{4\pi GB}{5} < c^2(1+k^2)$), the acceleration is negative ($\ddot{R} < 0$), and the universe undergoes decelerated expansion. The magnitude of this deceleration decreases as R increases.

If $K = 0$ (i.e., $\frac{4\pi GB}{5} = c^2(1+k^2)$), the acceleration is zero ($\ddot{R} = 0$), and the universe expands at a constant velocity. This scenario corresponds to a specific condition that is dynamically consistent with our initial assumption of $\frac{dR}{dt} = kc$ (constant velocity).

4) If $R = kct$, $\rho = \frac{D}{R^3}$, (k and D are constants)

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dt^2} = -\frac{4\pi GD}{5R^2} = -\frac{3GM_{fr}}{5R^2} \quad (104)$$

In this case, the acceleration is always negative, indicating that the expansion of the universe is decelerating. This is an expected result in a typical matter-dominated universe where mass is conserved.

5. Increase in dark energy

5.1. The ratio of increase in gravitational potential energy to increase in mass energy

To simplify the calculation, assuming a uniform density ρ , when the range R of gravitational interaction changes, let's calculate the change in mass energy and the change in gravitational potential energy.

$$\frac{d(Mc^2)}{dR} = 4\pi R^2 \rho c^2 \quad (105)$$

$$\frac{d(U_{gp})}{dR} = -\frac{16\pi^2 G}{3} R^4 \rho^2 = \left(-\frac{4\pi R^3 \rho G}{3Rc^2} \right) (4\pi R^2 \rho c^2) = -\frac{GM}{Rc^2} \left(\frac{d(Mc^2)}{dR} \right) \quad (106)$$

$$\frac{d(U_{gp})}{dR} = -\frac{R_S}{2R} \frac{d(Mc^2)}{dR} \quad (107)$$

R_S is the Schwarzschild radius of the black hole formed by mass M .

The size of the event horizon formed by the mass distribution of $46.5Gly$ is $477.8Gly$.

$$\frac{d(U_{gp})}{dR} = -\frac{R_S}{2R} \left(\frac{d(Mc^2)}{dR} \right) = -\frac{477.8Gly}{2(46.5Gly)} \left(\frac{d(Mc^2)}{dR} \right) = -(5.14) \left(\frac{d(Mc^2)}{dR} \right) \quad (108)$$

If the range of gravitational interaction increases and a positive mass is increases by ΔM , the equivalent mass of negative gravitational potential energy is increases by $-5.14\Delta M$. This value is not a fixed value, it depends on the density and the size of the range of gravitational interaction.

To find the ratio $-\frac{R_S}{2R}$ according to R , if $R = k \times Gly$,

$$\frac{\frac{d(U_{gp})}{dR}}{\frac{d(Mc^2)}{dR}} = -\frac{R_S}{2R} \quad (109)$$

$$R_S(k \times Gly) = \frac{2GM}{c^2} = (0.00475 \times Gly)(k^3) \quad (110)$$

$R(Gly)$	$R_S(Gly)$	$-R_S/2R$
10	4.80	-0.238
15	16.0	-0.533
20	38.0	-0.950
25	74.2	-1.48
30	128	-2.13
35	204	-2.91
40	304	-3.80
45	433	-4.81
50	594	-5.94

The density used the current critical density, but the density is a variable. Please see the approximate trend. The rate of increase of gravitational potential energy tends to be greater than the rate of increase of mass energy. Therefore, at some point, a situation arises in which dark energy becomes larger than matter and dark matter.

By the way, the negative mass ratio of 5.14 produced is very similar to the ratio of matter : dark matter.

5.2. Increase in dark energy (gravitational potential energy) due to increase in the range of gravitational interactionn

Figure 3: The past range of gravitational interaction, the present range of gravitational interaction, and $R_{gp} = 21.4Gly$ (The inflection point calculated assuming 1.5 times the current average density), the inflection point at which the magnitudes of repulsive and attractive forces are equal. When the range of gravitational interaction is smaller than R_{gp} , the attractive component is dominant, and when the range of gravitational interaction is larger than R_{gp} , the repulsive component (gravitational potential energy) is dominant.

5.2.1. Matters and galaxies spread almost uniformly throughout the universe through the inflation process.

5.2.2. Matters and galaxies move according to the Hubble-Lemaitre law. On the other hand, the propagation speed of the field, the range of gravitational interaction, has the fastest speed, the speed of light in expanding space.

5.2.3. Thus, over time, many new substances (matters and galaxies, or vacuum energy ...) enter the range of gravitational interaction. In other words, the newly entering materials (or energy) undergo gravitational interaction, resulting in an increase in mass (or energy) and an increase in gravitational potential energy in the region within the range of gravitational interaction.

5.2.4. By the way, **while mass energy is proportional to M , total gravitational potential energy (gravitational self-energy) is proportional to $-\frac{M^2}{R}$** . As M increases, the gravitational potential energy (absolute value) increases faster. Accordingly, the repulsive force component increases faster than the attractive force component.

5.2.5. The increase in gravitational potential energy (absolute value) due to the newly incorporated mass (energy) into the range of gravitational interaction results in an increase in dark energy. The same principle applies to the birth of energy or vacuum expectation value within the range of gravitational interaction. That is, when the mass energy increases by M , the absolute value of gravitational potential energy increases by $-\frac{M^2}{R}$. In this model, even if a mass is born while satisfying energy conservation in a local area, as the new gravitational field propagates, the gravitational interaction with other matter will increase. Accordingly, an increase in the absolute value of gravitational potential energy may occur.

The same principle can be applied to vacuum energy. **Vacuum energy (or vacuum expectation value) may also be present in this model. At this time, the vacuum energy with a positive energy density does not have a negative pressure, but has a negative gravitational potential energy.**

5.2.6. In the present universe, it is predicted that the dark energy effect (repulsive effect) surpassed the gravitational effect of matter and dark matter about 5 ~ 7 billion years ago. According to this model, it is the point at which the positive mass energy and the negative gravitational potential energy are equal. Knowing the average density function, we can get the exact value.

5.2.7. Gravitational potential energy is a concept that already exists and is negative energy that can create repulsive force. **This model produces similar results to the phenomenon of applying negative pressure while having positive inertial mass.** As the universe ages and the range of gravitational interaction increases, the positive mass energy increases (new influx or birth of matter), but the negative gravitational potential energy created by these positive mass energy is greater.

6. Two periods of accelerated expansion, the early inflation period and the late dark energy period

In the history of the universe, we know that there have been two periods of accelerated expansion. However, both periods of accelerated expansion require repulsion on a cosmic scale. Therefore, rather than explaining the two periods of accelerated expansion with two different factors, there is a desire to explain them with one factor, that is, one dark energy model.

In the gravitational potential energy model, dark energy has a density $\rho^2(t)$ term. Therefore, at high densities during inflationary periods, the dark energy term becomes very large. Therefore, the gravitational potential energy model has the potential to simultaneously explain periods of inflation and dark energy [13].

$$\Lambda(t_P) = 8.66 \times 10^{69} m^{-2} \quad (111)$$

$$\Lambda(t_{now}) = 1.1056 \times 10^{-52} m^{-2} \quad (112)$$

$$\frac{\Lambda(t_P)}{\Lambda(t_{now})} = \frac{8.66 \times 10^{69} m^{-2}}{1.1056 \times 10^{-52} m^{-2}} = 7.83 \times 10^{121} \quad (113)$$

This is due to the nature of gravitational potential energy. When R increases while M is constant, the absolute value of gravitational potential energy decreases, and when M increases, the absolute value of gravitational potential energy increases.

In the early universe, after inflation occurred when negative gravitational potential energy exceeded positive energy, if the radius of gravitational interaction increases due to rapid initial expansion of the universe while the mass M is almost constant, the absolute value of negative gravitational potential energy decreases. Therefore, negative gravitational potential energy becomes smaller than positive mass energy, and the inflation mechanism ends.

Due to the accelerated expansion of the early universe, when matter and energy are distributed almost uniformly throughout the universe, over time, the radius R of gravitational interaction gradually increases, and when the mass and energy that participate in gravitational interaction increases, accelerated expansion (dark energy phenomenon) occurs again.

Inflation and dark energy have the same origin, and it is gravitational potential energy or gravitational self-energy.

7. The future of the universe

In the standard cosmological Λ CDM model [4], dark energy is an object with uniform energy density. Thus, this universe will forever accelerating expansion.

In the gravitational potential energy model, the source of dark energy is the energy of the gravitational field or gravitational potential energy. The gravitational potential energy is proportional to $-M^2/R$, and if there is no inflow of mass from outside the system, absolute value of gravitational potential energy can decrease. From the point where the velocity of the field and the velocity of matter become the same, there is no inflow of matter from the outside of the system. On the other hand, as R increases, the absolute value of gravitational potential energy decreases.

Therefore, in the gravitational potential energy model, the universe does not accelerate forever, but at a certain point in the future, it stops the accelerated expansion and enters the period of decelerated expansion. However, the universe will not shrink back to a very small area like the time of the Big Bang, but will maintain a certain size or more ($r \geq R_{gp}$) [14]. Its size depends on R_{gp} produced by the positive mass energy within the range of gravitational interaction.

If there is something like vacuum energy (with positive pressure, not negative pressure) in the universe, it also has the effect of increasing the mass of the system. In this case, the expansion of the universe can go on forever.

8. How to validate the dark energy model that gravitational potential energy is the dark energy

8.1. Find the values of $\rho(t)$ and $R(t)$

$\rho(t)$ is the average density of the area under consideration, and $R(t)$ is the range of gravitational interaction. The $R(t)$ used by this model is an estimated value based on the current observation result. If the basic values of current cosmology change, $R(t)$ and $\rho(t)$ can change.

The key point is that the positive energy (or mass) distribution itself has a gravitational potential energy with a negative value. And, this gravitational potential energy (or gravitational field's energy) is the source of dark energy.

8.2. At each time, within the $R(t)$

Find $E(t) = M(t)c^2$ and $U_{gp}(t) = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM(t)^2}{R(t)} \beta(t)$

$E(t) = M(t)c^2$ is the attractive energy component and $U_{gp}(t)$ is the repulsive energy component.

8.3. Compare $\frac{U_{gp}(t)}{E(t)}$ with the observations

Compare $\frac{U_{gp}(t)}{E(t)}$ with the observations. And for the inflection point transitioning from decelerated expansion to accelerated expansion, the theoretical value and the observed value are compared.

8.4. It is necessary to verify the Friedmann equations and the dark energy function

In the gravitational potential energy model, the dark energy is a function of time. Therefore, if the dark energy effect is precisely observed, it is possible to determine whether the model is right or wrong.

$$\frac{\Lambda(t)c^2}{3} = \frac{\beta(t)}{15} \left(\frac{4\pi GR(t)\rho(t)}{c} \right)^2 = 3 \left(\frac{2\pi GR\rho}{5c} \right)^2 \quad (114)$$

In addition, the model predicts inflection points that change from decelerated to accelerated expansion, where the magnitude of the positive energy and the negative gravitational potential energy produced by this positive energy become equal. By verifying this inflection point, this model can be verified.

However, there is a difficult problem. Most of the equations of motion come from the conservation law. However, in the Gravitational Potential Energy Model, the positive equivalent mass inside the radius R of the gravitational interaction changes with time. Therefore, the negative equivalent mass of the gravitational potential energy created by this positive equivalent mass also changes. It is difficult for me to establish the equations of motion of the test mass in this state.

The dark energy term obtained here also only presents the value of the dark energy term at a specific time. Therefore, when inferring the value of dark energy in the past through this equation, we should not assume and estimate that the mass inside the shell is conserved. We need to establish a new equation of motion.

Recently, there are claims that the w value of dark energy is not -1, but $w = -0.903$. This suggests that the cosmological constant model may be wrong [15].

Observation results of 1499 supernovae by the DES (Dark Energy Survey) team (2024.01)

The standard cosmological model is known as Λ CDM, or ‘Lambda cold dark matter’. This mathematical model describes how the Universe evolves using just a few features such as the density of matter, the type of matter and the behavior of dark energy. While Λ CDM assumes the density of dark energy in the Universe is constant over cosmic time and doesn’t dilute as the Universe expands, the DES Supernova Survey results hint that this may not be true.

they also hint that dark energy might possibly be varying. “There are tantalizing hints that dark energy changes with time,” said Davis, “We find that the simplest model of dark energy - Λ CDM - is not the best fit. It’s not so far off that we’ve ruled it out, but in the quest to understand what is accelerating the expansion of the Universe this is an intriguing new piece of the puzzle. A more complex explanation might be needed.” [16]

BAO observation results by the DESI (Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument) team (2024.04)

“It’s not yet a clear confirmation, but the best fit is actually with a time-varying dark energy,” said Palanque-Delabrouille of the results. “What’s interesting is that it’s consistent over the first three points. The dashed curve [see graph above] is our best fit, and that corresponds to a model where dark energy is not a simple constant nor a simple Lambda CDM dark energy but a dark energy component that would vary with time. [17]

9. Conclusion

When a bound object exerts gravity, the gravitational action of gravitational potential energy (gravitational binding energy) is also included. Therefore, even in the case of the universe, we have to calculate the gravitational action of gravitational potential energy or gravitational field’s energy. Since gravitational potential energy has a negative equivalent mass, gravitational potential energy creates a repulsive force. If the gravitational potential

energy or gravitational field's energy is greater than the positive mass energy, it can be a candidate for dark energy to explain the current accelerated expansion. And, when we calculated the gravitational potential energy for the observable universe, it is approximately three times larger than the positive mass energy, so it can explain the accelerated expansion of the universe.

Positive energy is an attractive component, and the Negative energy (gravitational potential energy) is a repulsive component. Therefore, if $|(-M_{gp})c^2| < Mc^2$, there is a decelerated expansion, and if $|(-M_{gp})c^2| > Mc^2$, accelerated expansion is performed. $|(-M_{gp})c^2| = Mc^2$ is the inflection point from the decelerated expansion to the accelerated expansion.

The effect of dark energy occurs because all positive energy (matter, radiation, (if present) vacuum energy...) entering the range of gravitational interaction produces negative gravitational potential energy. Since the total mass in the range of gravitational interaction is proportional to M , whereas the gravitational potential energy is proportional to $-\frac{M^2}{R}$, the repulsive force component increases faster and accelerated expansion occurs. This model can be verified because it points to the gravitational potential energy and the range of gravitational interaction as the causes. This model predicts an inflection point where dark energy becomes larger and more important than the energy of matter and radiation. Also, dark energy is presented as a function of time.

The key argument of this paper is that when a positive mass density $+\rho$ exists, then there is an equivalent mass density $-\rho_{gp}$ of the gravitational potential energy or the gravitational field energy, created by this positive mass density. And, the equivalent mass density of the gravitational potential energy or the gravitational field energy is the source of dark energy.

If there is a change in the observed value of the positive mass density (such as the critical density), the size of the interaction range can change.

There is no cosmological constant. Dark energy does not have a constant energy density, and the density of dark energy is a function of time. The source of dark energy is the gravitational potential energy or the energy-momentum of the gravitational field.

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